

Deliverable D9.4.

REPORT ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Deliverable report

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
RM	Raw Materials
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PCO	Project Coordinator
RP	Reporting Period
SLO	Social License to Operate

1 Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities of the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

This deliverable will be updated in months 24, 36 and 48 to keep the strategies set in D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan up to date.

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium will combine the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates industry, to enhance Health & Safety conditions for workers, to improve the Process and Efficiency of the aggregates extractive sites, to maximise Sustainability and Resource Efficiency in the quarry operations and to foster Social Acceptance.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

This document describes the current status of the overall awareness raising process, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and partners' responsibilities. It includes specific actions and activities that have been carried out by the DIGIECOQUARRY consortium members to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results.

With that said, this deliverable outlines (see Figure 2):

- **What** has been disseminated. Devoting to the basic project-related information that will be conveyed throughout the project.
- To **whom** the project has been disseminate to. Consisting of the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.
- **How** the project has been disseminated. Including all the channels and tools that will be used by project partners to successfully implement the dissemination activities.
- **When** the project has been disseminated. Providing the time frame to ensure that the timing of the dissemination activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project and beyond.
- **Monitoring** of the process. Indicating the indicators to gauge success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project [Dissemination, communication, exploitation plan DCEP].

Figure 2. DCEP strategy.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled ‘D9.4: Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities’, aims to follow up on the designed strategy, plan and activities implemented under the DIGIECOQUARRY project, whose goal is to maximise the project’s visibility and impact.

With the plans and actions described, the DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium aims to meet the following dissemination objectives:

- To effectively promote the project and its results to all possible target groups and audiences at national and a European level.
- To establish links and liaisons with international organisations and other interested stakeholders to provide wider dissemination.
- To establish synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives.
- To validate the project outcomes, to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies and actions are the cornerstone for generating a deep impact of the DIGIECOQUARRY results in terms of attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and social acceptance.

To maximise the impact beyond the project lifetime, these actions will be undertaken within three WPs: WP7. Mechanisms for social acceptance and interaction with policy makers; WP8. Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on RM; and WP9. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation.

These activities will be articulated with 4 master plans: [1] Clustering plan, [2] Dissemination strategy, [3] Communication strategy and [4] Exploitation strategy (all of them based on D9.1).

2.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

WP9 works closely with WP7 and WP8. Coordination meetings are regularly held to monitor the results achieved within the social, clustering, dissemination, communication and exploitation results.

Figure 3. Relationship between WPs.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities” is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary. Contains a brief fact sheet about the project.

Section 2 – Introduction. Provides meaningful information regarding the DCEP and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables.

Section 3 – Dissemination assets.

Section 4 – Target groups.

Section 5 – Dissemination and communication activities.

Section 6 – Key performance indicators.

Section 7 – Timetable.

Section 8 - Conclusions: Summarises the conclusions of this report as well as the way forward.

Annexes

2.4 Partners’ role in the dissemination strategy

DIGIECOQUARRY partners and their strategic positioning in Europe (and also ASOGRAVAS and MINTEK in Colombia and South Africa, respectively) count with vast capacities to influence the target communities and will act as multipliers. Table 1 summarises the main dissemination strategies to be implemented:

PARTNERS	DISSEMINATION STRATEGY
Large companies: SANDVIK, METSO, MAXAM, AKKA	They have an important influence and impact in the aggregates industry, quarry technology providers, construction and complementary sectors (such as OEMs and 1 st tier providers) including their client networks and commercialisation channels. Dissemination will focus on engaging potential customers interested in exploiting product/services generated.
SMEs: ITK, ARCO, MAESTRO, DH&P, ABAUT, APP, SIGMA, ZABALA	They are mainly interested in attracting new clients and reinforcing the loyalty of customer portfolio thanks to the new competitive advantages acquired related to the KTAs and the IQS. SMEs will make available to DIGIECOQUARRY their existing client/supplier networks as well as the involvement of their Marketing and Communication departments.
Quarries: VICAT, HANSON, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR	They are eager to extend their client portfolio and strengthen links with the already existing ones. Their Dissemination actions will be based on the presentation of improved products (in quality, economic, environmental and social terms) to engage specific stakeholders and end users, mainly in the construction sector (e.g., cement, RMC, road base and subbase, mortar, asphalt, etc). Also, they would like to influence positively the perception of quarrying in the society (see section 2.3).
R&D and Academia: MUL, CHALMERS, UPM, MINTEK, ROCTIM	They aim at engaging with the EU (and also international) scientific and industrial communities to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation and sharing. They pursue the generation of new research lines and training programmes aligned with the key pillars established in H2020. They are seeking to Involve their research groups and communication departments in dissemination activities. Reinforcement of the EU RM’ sector.
International cooperation, Promoters & Public bodies: ANEFA, DGASTUR, ASOGRAVAS	They will engage with their network of contacts to maximise their dissemination impact by using their wide partners network, benefiting from their experience/expertise in meetings, workshops and conferences to establish contact and bound relations with target groups of the wide range of themes of DIGIECOQUARRY. They would like to bridge the gap between science, practice and society by organising targeted stakeholder workshops to bring together stakeholders, industry, policy makers and citizens to facilitate public acceptance.

Table 1. Dissemination Strategy per partner profile.

3 Dissemination Assets

The Project’s assets and outcomes that are here described, have been disseminated by all partners with a view to maximise the project’s impact and visibility. This information is being conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each stakeholder group, in order to promote not only the DIGIECOQUARRY’s results, but also its vision and aim.

- The **conceptual aspects** of the project, meaning the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both on business and at social level, etc.
- The **technical achievements of the project** like the DIGIECOQUARRY IQS platform and the respective ICT infrastructure and needed toolkits. The assets of this category will be highly disseminated on appropriate channel once these tools are developed and thus a more detailed communication strategy will be contained in the next version of the DCEP.
- The **scientific knowledge** that derives from the project in the form of reports, scientific articles, etc.
- All the spectrum of the **project’s activities**, like the four workshops that will be organized in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY, the closing event, the participation in external events and every other action that could be of interest to the project’s target groups.

Figure 4. DIGIECOQUARRY's dissemination assets

4 Target groups

The key stakeholders of DIGIECOQUARRY can be segmented into the four target groups outlined below. The actual stakeholders have been identified and registered in a stakeholders Excel worksheet.

- **Business stakeholders:** with potential interest in the project’s successful execution and results that will expand the project’s scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.
- **Academic and research stakeholders:** Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **Governmental and policy stakeholders:** policy makers are of primary interest for the consortium given that they are responsible for setting the guidelines of the current and future mining policies that will affect the commercial feasibility of DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **General public stakeholders:** non-governmental organizations, civil society groups or simply citizens, interested in the potential of DIGIECOQUARRY to address needs relevant to them.

Figure 5. DIGIECOQUARRY's stakeholders.

TARGET AUDIENCE	AIM	KEY MESSAGES
1. Aggregates industries & Quarries / RM Stakeholders and end users Material providers Industry associations and representatives	Final users of DIGIECOQUARRY's result Commercial exploitation Project involvement Clustering via WP8	Main results and experience from pilots Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Economic, investment & cost analysis Prospects of prolonging the productive life cycles of quarries
2. ICT industry Technology providers Associations and representatives	New range of services in Quarrying the quarry sector Commercial exploitation Open and flexible methodologies for interoperability of ICT tools	Main results and experience reports from the pilots Available materials/services and knowledge generated
3. Researchers at universities, R&D centres or and Scientific societies in RM	Enhanced scientific knowledge R&D cooperation and promotion Clustering via WP8	Increase data available for research Main results shared in EURMKB and RMIS
4. Construction sector and other clients	Promote the development of new or improved products and services based on DIGIECOQUARRY results	Improved cost-efficient products, H&S, social & environmental KPIs Raise awareness
5. Citizens and civil society	General awareness Social License to Operate (SLO) Project involvement via WP7	Community Engagement Strategies Social Awareness plan Local engagement plan
6. Policy makers and funding bodies (Government, Regulatory agencies) at local, national and EU level	Provide strong evidence to establish new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for RM Interaction in WP7	Reinforcement of the Quarrying sector Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Raise awareness
7. Media, journalists and other groups at European level (e.g., environment, energy, safety, NGOs, Consumer's organisations...)	General awareness Improved perception of the extractive industry Trend setters	Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Available materials/services for communication purposes

Table 2. Target audiences, aims and key messages.

A preliminary list of identified stakeholders is included in Annex I of D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.

5 Dissemination and Communication activities

5.1 Publications

5.1.1 Press releases

DEQ's website releases at least a monthly press clip about the latest updates of the project. They can be found in 'News' section. They are also available in Annex III.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/noticias-deq/>

5.1.2 Dissemination and communication articles in journals and magazines

In the coming months, an article about DEQ will be included in the International Cement Review. Also, articles about the project have been written in the online magazine '*ANEFA Actualidad*' and paper magazines '*Rocas y Minerales*' and '*Stein und Kies*'. They can be found in Annex IV.

5.1.3 Scientific publications

So far, a joint article between UPM - M and Maxam has been published in Elsevier under the title of 'A novel borehole surveying system for underground mining: Design and performance assessment'. It is an Open Access publication which is available at the following link:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224122002895>

5.1.4 Public deliverables

Several deliverables have been submitted to the European Commission for their assessment. The ones that can be shared with the general public are uploaded on the project website:

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/deliverables/>

5.2 Participation in events, trade fairs and workshops

During these months, DIGIECOQUARRY's consortium partners have participated in some external events to publicise the carried out activities and results.

A list of identified events, fairs and workshops can be found in D9.1 Annex XII.

5.2.1 Joint Research Centre (JRC) Training Webinar: held in collaboration between Mintek and Beijing General Research Institute of Mining & Metallurgy

The JRC was created in 2018 as a conduit for collaborative research on minerals resources between South African and Chinese research institutes. One of the means of knowledge transfer is to hold regular meetings, taking the form of mini-seminars. At one of these meetings, held on 21 October 2021, Mintek gave an overview presentation on the digital twinning concept proposed as part of the DIGIECOQUARRY project, which was well received although it does not currently form part of the JRC portfolio of research.

5.2.2 SMOPYC

ANEFA set up a stand at SMOPYC, International Show of Public Works, Construction and Mining Machinery (17 to 19 November 2021 – Zaragoza – Spain) and offered several materials about the project.

Figure 6. DEQ in SMOPYC.

5.2.3 MIRO Forum

German partners ITK and Dohmen, Herzog & Partner, attended and set up a stand at the MIRO Forum, held from the 24th to 26th of November in Berlin, Germany.

Figure 7. DEQ in MIRO Forum.

5.2.4 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)"

DIGIECOQUARRY Project participated in the 2021 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop “Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)” which was held online on December 3rd.

The aim of this workshop was to facilitate the efficient knowledge transfers from EU projects on raw materials (such as Horizon 2020/Europe, and EIT Raw Materials projects) into the RMIS, so that that project’s outputs can best contribute to the RMIS & EU policy objectives. More information can be found [here](#).

5.2.5 Spanish Geology Olympics

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project joined recently one of the exciting qualifications for the Spanish Geology Olympics. Students and teachers took part in the different competitions held at Madrid’s School of Mines and Energy on the 3rd of March 2022.

Important information and issues related to aggregates and quarries could not be missed in such an important event. In addition, topics about digitalization were widely discussed and practical examples were made to develop 3D models of minerals and rocks.

Figure 8. DEQ in the Spanish Geology Olympics

5.2.6 Expominerals

DIGIECOQUARRY took part in an educational event with a heterogeneous public during the ExpoMinerals exhibition held at Madrid's School of Mines and Energy on the 13th of March 2022. During this event, we presented some of the main characteristics of aggregates and quarries. In addition, we brought up several topics about digitalization, explaining the processes involved in it and presenting some practical examples involving the development of 3D models of minerals and rocks.

ExpoMinerals is one of the most important exhibitions of raw materials in Spain. Visitors can learn about fossils, gems or meteorites from all over the world that make it the perfect place to connect with collectors, geologists and students. As a result, it is the best way to contact with kids and teenagers and illustrate them about everything related to minerals.

Figure 9. DEQ in Expominerals.

5.2.7 South African Institute of Quarrying Conference

One of the attendees of the above-mentioned JRC webinar is a member of the Southern African Institute of Quarrying, so a presentation at their annual conference and exhibition held on 16 March 2022. This presentation provided technical details, suitable to the audience. Afterwards, two members from the audience indicated their interest in the topic, suggesting that they might ask for cooperation in future.

5.2.8 Raw Materials for the Green Transition

EIT RawMaterials, a key actor to advance Europe's transition to a sustainable economy, and the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) School of Mines hosted a panel discussion on the potential of Spain for responsible mining and metallurgy.

The conference served to inform both Spanish policy makers and industry representatives about the relevant aspects of the European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA) and its opportunities, as well as highlighting the importance of raw materials for the European industry and the potential of Spain to have a prominent role in securing raw materials for the green transition.

Here, WP8 leader presented DIGIECOQUARRY as an innovative sustainable quarrying system.

5.2.9 Field trips of the School of Mines and Energy of Madrid

WP8 leader has been involved in several dissemination activities concerning the DIGIECOQUARRY project:

During a recent school's visit to the School of Mines and Energy of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, children were introduced to the main features of aggregates as well as the scope of DIGIECOQUARRY. For their easy understanding, teen-adapted informative leaflets were distributed. (7 April).

A UPM School of Mines and Energy geological engineering field trip which included a visit to some quarries, where leaflets about aggregates were shared (9-11 April).

UPM School of Mines and Energy also paid visits and distributed leaflets during a trip with students to a few rehabilitated quarries and quarries currently under exploitation, to discuss the main aspects about the extractive sector (21 April).

Figure 10. Field trips of the School of Mines of Madrid

5.2.10 XIII Iberian Geochemical Congress

In this scientific conference, an oral presentation about the characteristics of limestones from lacustrine deposits in Central Spain was made. As one of the project's pilot sites shares this geological features, DEQ was widely explained.

5.2.11 European Minerals Days

Every two years, the European Minerals Days (EMDs) allows the European public to explore the world of minerals. It is a pan-European awareness initiative by the European minerals sector and related organisations. ANEFA lead the organisation of the workshops -about circular economy and environment- carried out in Leza del Río Leza (La Rioja, Spain) which brought together up to 300 people.

Figure 11. DEQ in European Minerals Days.

5.3 DIGIECOQUARRY's workshops, seminars & panel presentations

A list of identified workshops, seminars & panel presentations can be found in D9.1 Annex XIV.

5.3.1 VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos

The first DIGIEQUARRY workshop, organised by ANEFA, took place during the Spanish Aggregates Congress, hold in Oviedo (Spain) on Thursday 26 of May 2022.

Figure 12. Workshop's opening.

Figure 13. Workshop's speakers.

The workshop's plan was the following:

PROGRAMA DE SESIONES							
Un Congreso orientado a los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible							
JUEVES 26							
Auditorio afapa	Sala CRISTAL	Sala 1	Sala 2	Sala 7	Sala 8	Zona Exposición Comercial	
15:30	WORKSHOP DigIEcoQuarry Áridos 4.0 Moderador: D. César Luaces Frades - Director General de ANEFA - Coordinador del Proyecto	MESA REDONDA VII Cerrando el círculo de la economía circular Moderadora: D ^a . Rita Martínez Andía - Responsable de atención a empresas - ANEFA	MESA REDONDA VIII Retos de futuro de la industria de las rocas y minerales industriales PARTE II El reto de la sostenibilidad Moderador: D. Isidoro Miranda - Director General - LafargeHolcim España	SESIÓN 15 Explotaciones de áridos Presidente: D. Miguel Alonso Pérez - Presidente - AFAPA Moderador: D. Carlos Martínez Torres - ARIGAL	SESIÓN 13 Acceso a los recursos Presidente: D. Javier Fernández Lareño - Secretario General - UGT Asturias Moderadora: D ^a . Pilar Martín Boluda - Gerente - AFARCYL	SESIÓN 14 Seguridad y salud en el trabajo Presidente: D. Marcos Osorio Gómez - Presidente - Comité de Seguridad y Salud de ANEFA Moderadora: D ^a . Rosa Carretón Moreno - Directora Técnica - ANEFA	Exposición comercial
15:40	Implementación del concepto drill to mill D. Pablo Segarra Catasús - Titular Universidad - ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid	Ilma, Sra. D ^a . Nieves Roqueñí Gutiérrez - Viceconsejera de Medio Ambiente y Cambio Climático - Principado de Asturias D ^a . Marta Gómez Palenque - Directora de Economía Circular - Junta de Comunidades de Castilla - La Mancha	D. Pedro Mora Peris - Director de Industria - OFICEMEN D. Manuel Reguelo González Barro - Presidente - Ilustre Colegio Oficial de Geólogos y Consejeros Técnicos - Vicepresidencia de Relaciones Internacionales - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	Calibración de arenas finas en húmedo D. Esteban Salgado Prieto - Advanced Mineral Processing, S.L.	La dirección facultativa en materia preventiva (responsabilidad individual) D. Ramón Hervás Fernández - PREVING	Buscando la excelencia en Seguridad a través de la tecnología D ^a . Rebeca Anzarina Gómez González - Votorantim Cimentos España	
15:50	Digitalización en equipos de perforación de superficie D. Enrique Mota López - Sandvik Española, S.A.	D. José Manuel Zapico García - Secretario General - CCOO Asturias D. Manuel Reguelo González Barro - Presidente - Ilustre Colegio Oficial de Geólogos y Consejeros Técnicos - Vicepresidencia de Relaciones Internacionales - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	Selección del tipo de explosivo para voladuras en canteras de áridos. Empleo racional de la carga a granel D. Manuel Fonseca García - MAXAM	Beneficios de generar tu propia energía en el sector de los Áridos. Energía Solar Fotovoltaica. Impulsa tu negocio de una forma sostenible D. Ernesto Macías Galán - Solarwatt Spain / Ruano Energía S.L.	Objetivo, Cero Accidentes D. Aitor Puente de Cabo - ARIGAL		
16:00	Automatización de una planta de tratamiento de áridos D. Sergio Alonso Aznar - Departamento Internacional - Arco Electrónica	D. Santiago Sánchez Álvarez - Presidente - AFARCYL D. José Ignacio Tertre Torán - Presidente - RCD Asociación y Board Member de FIR	D. Jorge Aladro Vico - Director General - ANCADE	Tecnología de proceso de recuperación de ultrafinos D. Enrique María Carrasco Arroyo - Advanced Mineral Processing, S.L.	La transmisibilidad administrativa de los derechos mineros en tramitación D. Gonzalo Martín Morales de Castilla - Consejería de Industria, Empleo y Promoción Económica - Principado de Asturias		
16:10	DIGIECOQUARRY: el futuro del sector de los áridos ya es el presente D ^a . Lorena Villadés Santos - ANEFA - Coordinadora del Proyecto	D. Joel García Fernández - Presidente - Confederación Asturiana de la Construcción	D. Diego López González - Director General Materiales de Construcción - Cerámica Campo D. Ángel García de la Cal - Director General - Canteras de Santander, S.A. - Grupo CANDESA	Planes anuales de labores: revisión crítica de una institución jurídico-minera en su 50 cumpleaños D. J. C. Valle Feijóo - Federación de Áridos	SAFEME4MINE: Sistema de mantenimiento preventivo para elementos de seguridad de maquinaria minera D ^a . Natalia Vázquez Viñuela - Laboratorio Oficial José María de Madariaga (LOM)		
16:20	Digitalización en la industria de los áridos - Implantación usos y casos de éxito D. Paulo Romero Martínez - ANEFA - Coordinador del Proyecto	Debate	D. Iñigo de Amerasu y Fernández de Casadevante - Responsable de Comunicación - ANEFA	Reglamento de Urbanismo de Castilla y León: Modificación y Aplicación D ^a . Pilar Martín Boluda - AFARCYL	Seguimiento en la percepción de la cultura de seguridad D. Juan Carlos Pereira Fernández - Sibelco Minerales, S.A.		
16:30	DigIEcoQuarry como herramienta de monitoreo de las actividades de la flota móvil en minería D. Diego Ignacio Laza Martín - Mining Project Manager - Abaut	Debate	Proyecto Ageing@ Work, envejecimiento en el trabajo D ^a . María Loech de Lapuerta - ANEFA	Revisión crítica de las licencias municipales en el sector minero D. Julio César Valle Feijóo - Federación de Áridos	Proyecto DESA, siempre preparados D. Aitor Puente de Cabo - ARIGAL		
16:40	Visión de las explotaciones piloto del DigIEcoquarry Mr. Paolo Zambianchi - Holcim Italia		Real Support: hacia dónde van las explotaciones de áridos D. Jorge Balcázar García - Hispano Japonesa Maquinaria - HJM	Ley de Impulso para la Sostenibilidad del Territorio de Andalucía: Una oportunidad para la minería D. Carlos Ramírez Sánchez - AFA Andalucía	Teoría sobre la simplicidad para la prevención eficaz de riesgos en el uso de explosivos D. Salvador González Solís - MAXAM		
16:50	La digitalización y cooperación en el Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY D. José Eugenio Ortiz Menéndez - Catedrático - ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid		Debate	Debate	Debate		
17:00							

Figure 14. Workshop's plan.

<https://www.congresoaridos.com/auditorio-afapa>

You can watch the full recorded session at our YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UV7I4oFZgF4>

5.3.2 Capacity Building Programme (CBP) oriented to potential users and adopters

This will comprise video tutorials, a Massive Online Open Course – MOOC, a simulator for professionals and virtual workshops with third parties, that will be detailed later.

Currently, a joint team of WP7, WP8 and WP9 members is developing the MOOC. This first version will be in Spanish language, available at Madrid's School of Mines, oriented to both university and graduate students. Further on, a wider-audience English version will be developed. The translated Spanish version's table of contents is shown here:

0. Module 0. MOOC's introduction.

1. Module 1. Origin.

- 1.1. History of aggregates.
- 1.2. Definition of aggregate.
- 1.3. Types of aggregates.
- 1.4. The rock cycle.
- 1.5. Aggregates – Sedimentary rocks.
- 1.6. Aggregates – Igneous rocks.
- 1.7. Aggregates – Metamorphic rocks.

2. Module 2. The aggregates sector.

- 2.1. Applicable legislation to the aggregates sector.
- 2.2. Types of aggregates sites.

3. Module 3. Extraction of aggregates.

- 3.1. Extraction: mechanical and drilling and blasting.
- 3.2. Loading and hauling.

4. Module 4. Treatment of aggregates.

- 4.1. Crushing and milling.
- 4.2. Screening.
- 4.3. Washing and other humid processes.
- 4.4. Stocking and handling.

5. Module 5. Applications of aggregates.

- 5.1. Applications I. Aggregates for bituminous mixtures, bases, and sub-bases.
- 5.2. Applications II. Aggregates for concrete and mortar.
- 5.3. Applications III. Aggregates for ballast and rockfill.
- 5.4. Applications IV. Light and special aggregates.
- 5.5. Applications V. Industrial aggregates: Limestone and silica.

6. Module 6. Aggregates processing.

- 6.1. Quality processes.
- 6.2. Industrial security.
- 6.3. Added value.

7. Module 7. Digitalisation

- 7.1. Digital transformation and not digitalisation.
- 7.2. Model Vs Data.
- 7.3. Data cycle.
- 7.4. Possible approaches.
- 7.5. Mining cycle technological map.
- 7.6. Theoretical base.
- 7.7. Tools, languages and infrastructure.
- 7.8. Problems.
- 7.9. Generalisation of advanced problems and techniques.
- 7.10. Methodologies.
- 7.11. Use cases.

8. Module 8. Environment.

- 8.1. Environmental legislation.
- 8.2. Biodiversity management in quarries.

9. Module 9. Social dimension

- 9.1. Introduction to extractive activities' social dimension: Main impacts of the extractive industry in society.
- 9.2. Keys for a sustainable socioeconomic extractive sector: International framework.
- 9.3. Generating a positive social impact through the extractive sector: Best practices.
- 9.4. Social License to Operate: Local communities' acceptance and relationships.

5.4 On-line presence

5.4.1 Project's social media accounts & network with partner's social media profiles

Nowadays, social media accounts are considered key for the communication of the project. Since their creation, WP9 has been updating them by keeping up with DEQ's latest news and facts about the project.

DIGIECOQUARRY's social media URLs are:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Digiecoquarry>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiecoquarry/>

- Instagram: @digiecoquarry
- Twitter: @digi_eco
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>
- Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/digiecoquarry>

Direct access to DIGIECOQUARRY's social media is available on the website.

ANEFA administrates DIGIECOQUARRY's social media accounts, but all partners are required to actively interact with them, as well as to publish posts and news about DIGIECOQUARRY regularly through the social media of their organizations.

Partners' social media list is shown in D9.1. Annex XVI.

5.4.2 Videos

Five videos made out of drone flights have been uploaded to DEQ's Youtube channel and Vimeo. Their aim is to introduce the pilots and the technologies that will be developed in each of them to potential customers and interested stakeholders.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mw-UJVbvWAs>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zs9WFqjC9E8>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mr8sx9AfJe4>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8u20jWQ3ljA>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CeRF541H_5s

5.5 Other channels & tools

5.5.1 Partners' communication channels

DIGIECOQUARRY taps the support of partners' communication channels. During these months they have been publishing about the project in their social media, webpages, and intranets. In Annex V, ANEFA's (*ANEFA Online*) and SIGMA's publications are collected.

The list of Partners' communication channels is shown in D9.1 Annex XIX.

5.5.2 Synergies with relevant projects and initiatives

DIGIECOQUARRY has been disseminated within some clustering activities of other H2020 projects (see D9.3).

Moreover, the coordination team had an online meeting with NextGen SIMS project (<https://www.nexgensims.eu/?hotspot=0>). In this call, synergies between both projects were explored to look for a future business connexion.

WP8 leader, UPM – AI has held meetings and collaborated with some other raw materials related projects too, such as RM@Schools (<https://rmschools.isof.cnr.it/>), BetterGeoEdu (<https://www.bettergeoedu.com/>), and *Laboratorio virtual de minerales y rocas, Realidad extendida: recorridos virtuales y modelos geológicos 3D para asignaturas de Grados de Ciencias de la Tierra, GAMEinLABEX, DIG_IT*.

5.5.3 Meetings with neighbourhood or community reference groups

Local workshops and engagement actions will be organised in the pilot sites to introduce the project to local communities and consider their concerns and fears about the impact of the project.

WP7 is currently being helped by the pilot sites to organise the first of these meetings.

5.5.4 Meetings with policy makers (at EU and national levels)

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) closely collaborate and coordinate the organisation of meetings with policy makers at EU and national level to explain DIGIECOQUARRY. This aims to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation or other).

Information about DIGIECOQUARRY has been provided to the Raw Materials Knowledge Gateway (<https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/?page=rmkg>) in July 2021, including a supporting link to the website. Thus, in the RMIS there is a dedicated webpage space (Fig. 12) to showcase the project's raw materials-related knowledge. This content could be freely structured and displayed, so DEQ's logo and sections about different topics matching a short description were incorporated. Future updates will then be coordinated together with the RMKG, while close interaction with the RMIS team is taking place.

Figure 15. RMKG with the webpage space for EU funded Project including DIGIECOQUARRY.

6 KPIs

An evaluation of the KPIs for the implementation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan can be seen below.

DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN - DASHBOARD						
MONTH OF THE PROJECT		12				
KPI	(A)	(B)	(B-A)	(B/A%)	(B-A/48*Month of the project)	(B/(A/48*Month of the project))-1
	Final Target (Grant Agreement)	Number of actions related with KPI X implemented at the reference date	Absolute deviation from final target	Percentage of implementation	Relative deviation from average expected target	Relative % of deviation from average expected target
Participation in scientific conferences.	48	1	-47	2,08%	-11,00	-91,67%
Participation in events/ fairs/workshops.	26	13	-13	50,00%	6,50	100,00%
Scientific publications.	24	1	-23	4,17%	-5,00	-83,33%
Publications in paper magazines, websites and social media.	32	26	-6	81,25%	18,00	225,00%
Guidance roadmaps for the extractive industry.	3	0	-3	0,00%	-0,75	-100,00%
Open-door symposia.	10	0	-10	0,00%	-2,50	-100,00%
Joint co-creation meetings.	2	0	-2	0,00%	-0,50	-100,00%
Capacity Building Program.	1	0	-1	0,00%	-0,25	-100,00%
Training sessions.	3	0	-3	0,00%	-0,75	-100,00%
Project workshops.	4	1	-3	25,00%	0,00	0,00%
Global Innovation and Technology Conference in the RM sector.	1	0	-1	0,00%	-0,25	-100,00%
New sector and Expert Forum.	1	0	-1	0,00%	-0,25	-100,00%
Presentations in different Committee Meetings.	8	0	-8	0,00%	-2,00	-100,00%

Presentations in the Entrepreneurs Forum.	2	0	-2	0,00%	-0,50	-100,00%
Seminars & panel discussion & networking meeting in the Spanish National Aggregates Congress 2022 & 2025.	2	1	-1	50,00%	0,50	100,00%
Workshop in the ANEFA Chair in Aggregate Technology.	1	0	-1	0,00%	-0,25	-100,00%
Workshop in the European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining.	1	0	-1	0,00%	-0,25	-100,00%
Newsletters.	6	0	-6	0,00%	-1,50	-100,00%
Website updates in the project period.	6	1	-5	16,67%	-0,50	-33,33%
Meetings with neighbourhood or community reference group.	10	0	-10	0,00%	-2,50	-100,00%
Enquiries from citizens received.	40	0	-40	0,00%	-10,00	-100,00%
Policy makers: meetings at European level.	10	0	-10	0,00%	-2,50	-100,00%
Policy makers: 20 meetings at national level.	20	0	-20	0,00%	-5,00	-100,00%
Logo.	1	1	0	100,00%	0,75	300,00%
Project website.	1	1	0	100,00%	0,75	300,00%
Visits in the project website.	70000	0	-70000	0,00%	-17500,00	-100,00%
Followers in social media.	1000	330	-670	33,00%	80,00	32,00%
Communication materials/year.	24	11	-13	45,83%	5,00	83,33%
Press release, article, interview /year.	16	14	-2	87,50%	10,00	250,00%
Videos.	2	1	-1	50,00%	0,50	100,00%

As shown, some of the KPIs have not even started yet. This is due to the fact that for some of them the project needs further development, meaning the start of the field tests. It would be pointless to launch further scientific publications and technical conferences without any tangible results, or trainings sessions on a tool which is still being defined.

However, on the other hand, the Consortium has been very active participating in events, fairs, and publishing articles about the day-to-day of the project. So far, the Consortium has already achieved half of the required events attendance and three quarter of the needed publications in magazines and websites.

8 Conclusions

This document, titled “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities”, describes the activities and materials that have been done and produced during this months to disseminate DIGIECOQUARRY.

As the project evolves, this document will be updated in months 24, 36 and 48.

9 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- EU Horizon 2020 call.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium Agreement.

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Madrid Consortium Meeting November 2021

Madrid Consortium Meeting November 2021

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Madrid. Members of the DigiEcoQuarry consortium had the opportunity to meet in person on the 29th and 30th of last November in the auditorium of the ETSI Minas y Energía (Madrid, Spain). These facilities offered a perfect framework and an space with allowed social distance to develop this in-person meeting. It was also possible to follow the consortium meeting online. Face-to-face attendance was affected due to COVID-19 movement restrictions in some countries (and some companies), but the meeting managed to gather 41 members, and an average of 22 online.

In the course of the meeting, the WP leaders presented the progress made in the project according to their own work packages. At the end of each presentation, participants discussed the problems and difficulties encountered, concluding the analysis of each package with the proposal of next steps to be taken.

The general director of ANEFA, Cesar Luaces, as coordinator of the project, made the general balance of the meeting. The next actions were agreed:

- the partners (in charge of collecting the quarry data) will make available to the consortium examples of datasets, in order to share the features and formats of the files.
- realization of video tutorials (or demonstrations) to learn the possibilities and characteristics of the Expert Systems.
- scheduling the Technical Committee meeting (currently scheduled for 21st of December 2022).
- create and maintain procedures to facilitate communication and information exchange between partners (and between work packages).

All attendees highlighted the advantages of face-to-face interactions between members in addressing the next steps and challenges encountered so far.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2021/12/13/madrid-consortium-meeting-november-2021/>

Meeting of the Project Technical Committee

The Project Technical Committee (PTC) of the DigiEcoQuarry project met telematically on Tuesday 21st December. This meeting took place after the face-to-face event of the whole consortium that was held in the auditorium of the ETSI Minas y Energía of Madrid. The chief function of this committee is to supervise the correct development of the project. The meeting was attended by 19 people from the following partners: Holcim Agregati Calcestruzzi, Granulats Vicat, Akka High Tech, Dohmen Herzog & Partner, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Zabala Innovation Consulting and ANEFA.

The Project Technical Committee is composed of all the work package (WP) leaders of the DEQ project and chaired by ANEFA in its role as coordinator and MUL as co-leader. The PTC meets to gather information on the progress of the project and, in case of deviations, will advise the PMB (Project Management Board) on how to rearrange tasks and budgets. It will also support the PC (Project Coordinator) in preparing EC meetings and related data and products, preparing the contents and timing of press releases and joint publications, as well as reviewing all project documentation.

During this meeting, the work package leaders (1 to 5) discussed the risks that have been identified so far. As a result of the meeting, they defined the next steps to address the identified risks in order to ensure that they do not disrupt the development of the project.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/01/05/meeting-of-the-project-technical-committee/>

DIGIECOQUARRY participated in the 2021 JRC/HaDEA Technical Workshop

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DIGIECOQUARRY Project participated in the 2021 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)" which was held online on December 3rd.

The aim of this workshop was to facilitate the efficient knowledge transfers from EU projects on raw materials (such as Horizon 2020/Europe, and EIT Raw Materials projects) into the RMIS, so that that project's outputs can best contribute to the RMIS & EU policy objectives. More information can be found [here](#).

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/01/21/digiecoquarry-project-participated-in-the-2021-jrc-hadea-technical-workshop/>

Expert systems Online Training & Demo meetings

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Demonstration meetings have been organised during January and early February to showcase the Expert Systems (ES) software of several DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) partners, as agreed in the DEQ Technical Committee and consortium meeting in Madrid. These meetings aimed to show the current software capacity of each partner to the other partners of the consortium. These ES demonstrations have been carried out by the technical team of each partner and counted with an average attendance of more than 40 people. These meetings have allowed all the project partners to get to know in detail the technologies involved in the project. Special attention has been paid to the data that would be generated and the functionalities they have available, answering questions such as:

- What does your expert systems do? With special focus on inputs, outputs and functionalities: What do you measure? how do you measure it? how often do you measure it?
- Future steps: the improvements that are proposed to be developed in your expert system for the future
- How can they interact with other expert systems, the DEQ data lake and artificial intelligence?
- Anything that you consider relevant related to your expert system and its integration in DEQ

The demonstrations focused in particular on data analysis for e.g. fleet management, preventive monitoring of safety conditions, noise and dust control etc. and on proposed for improvements to be developed for the future in the DEQ project.

The systems that have been presented so far correspond to those of the following partners:

- ARCO electronics
- Roctim
- Dohmen, Herzog & Partner
- Abaut
- Maxam
- Metso: Outotec
- Ma-estro

After each presentation, there was a discussion among all the attendees.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/02/21/expert-systems-online-training-demo-meetings/>

Moving from theory to practice

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The European Union funded project DIGIECOQUARRY achieves its first milestone and begins an exciting new phase with both hands, and feet, on the job.

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in five pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalized, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The consortium behind DIGIECOQUARRY, formed by 25 organizations from eight different EU countries and two international partners, has just reached an important step related with the definition of all the initial requirements needed to evaluate and define the developments that will be implemented in the following stages of the project. It consists of all the deliverables of work gathered under the title: «Towards the digital innovative quarry – requirements for a sustainable, social, safe, resource-efficient quarrying operation» (package I) as well as the first deliverables from the section named: «Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers».

The deliverables that have just been fulfilled are associated with the implementation of the project and include a detailed analysis of the quarries where the technologies will be developed and tested (known as “pilot sites” in this project). Due to travel restrictions caused by Covid-19 preventative measures, most of the meetings took place via online which has implied an extra effort on the part of all participants. All these deliverables would not have been possible without the close collaboration of all the partners involved in the project.

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium combines the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates industry, to enhance Health & Safety conditions for workers, to improve the Process and

Efficiency of the aggregate's extractive sites, to maximize Sustainability and Resource Efficiency in the quarry operations and to foster Social Acceptance.

This phase includes the following deliverable reports that have just been completed:

D 1.1. «Requirements for improved extraction, rock mass characterization and control report» categorized as public dissemination and corresponding to task 1.1: “Requirements for Improved extraction, rock mass characterization and control and Innovative Treatment (crushing/screening/washing)”.

D 1.2. «Requirements for Innovative Treatment processes» listed as public dissemination (belongs to task 1.1).

D 1.3. «Requirements for Quarry full digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI report” listed as public dissemination. Which is included in task 1.2: «Requirements for Quarry full digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation and Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI)”.

D 1.4. «Requirements for H&S improvement, Environmental impact minimization and energy and resources efficiency report» listed as confidential (at this point access is reserved only for consortium members, including commission services). From Task 1.3: «Requirements for Health and Safety improvement, Environmental impact minimization and energy and resources (mineral, water & other) efficiency».

On the other hand, another report that has been completed is the one under the title: «Context narrative, social risk matrix and stakeholder mapping» part of task 7.1: «Social risk analysis in the 5 pilot sites» in which a deep study of the situation of each pilot site has been carried out.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/03/10/moving-from-theory-to-practice/>

Welcome to the Spanish Geology Olympics

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The DIGIECOQUARRY Project joined recently one of the exciting qualifications for the Spanish Geology Olympics. Students and teachers took part in the different competitions held at Madrid's School of Mines and Energy on the 3rd of March 2022.

Important information and issues related to aggregates and quarries could not be missed in such an important event. In addition, topics about digitalization were widely discussed and practical examples were made to develop 3D models of minerals and rocks.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/03/10/welcome-to-the-spanish-geology-olympics/>

DIGIECOQUARRY at ExpoMinerals

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DIGIECOQUARRY at ExpoMinerals

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The **DIGIECOQUARRY** Project took part in an educational event with a heterogenous public during the Expo Minerals exhibition held at Madrid's School of Mines and Energy on the 13th of March 2022. During this event, we presented some of the main characteristics of aggregates and quarries. In addition, we brought up several topics about digitalization, explaining the processes involved in it and presenting some practical examples involving the development of 3D models of minerals and rocks.

Expominerals is one of the most important exhibitions of raw materials in Spain. Visitors can learn about fossils, gems or meteorites from all over the world that make it the perfect place to connect with collectors, geologists and students. As a result, it is the best way to contact with kids and teenagers and illustrate them about everything related to minerals.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/04/06/digiecoquarry-at-expominerals/>

DIGIECOQUARRY strikes again

< Anterior

ANEFA, DIGIECOQUARRY's coordination team, has visited again two of its pilot sites: Fenouillet, owned by Granulats Vicat (Toulouse) and Alenquer, by Cimpor-Agrepor (Lisbon).

DIGIECOQUARRY has been funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme. It aims to design, develop, and validate an Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) in five pilot sites. The IQS is composed of sensors, processes, and tools, which will capture and process all the data arising throughout the aggregate production stages. This will allow, once the system is implemented, an integrated, digitalized, automatic and real-time control of the activities carried out in a quarry.

During these months, the actions to be carried out in each pilot site have been fine-tuned to tap the full potential of each one of them, that exactly has been the case of Vicat and Cimpor. ANEFA has held face-to-face meetings to redefine the role played by some of the partners in each of the quarries. After fruitful conferences, we can assure that DIGIECOQUARRY is stronger and more focused on success than ever.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/05/05/digiecoquarry-strikes-again/>

ANEFA actualidad no 68. Jan – Feb – Mar 2022

BREVES

El público de Anteproyectos de Ley de Cambio Climático en la Red

El Gobierno de España publicará a finales de este mes el primer borrador de la Ley de Cambio Climático que, a su vez, será sometida al proceso de participación pública. El primer borrador de esta Ley de Cambio Climático se publicará en la página web de la Ley de Cambio Climático y se mantendrá abierta a la participación pública durante un periodo de 30 días hábiles. El primer borrador de esta Ley de Cambio Climático se publicará en la página web de la Ley de Cambio Climático y se mantendrá abierta a la participación pública durante un periodo de 30 días hábiles.

La aprobación de una demografía a medida en Navarra

El pasado 1 de abril el Parlamento de Navarra aprobó una ley que garantiza una vivienda digna y adecuada para todos los navarros. Esta ley garantiza una vivienda digna y adecuada para todos los navarros. Esta ley garantiza una vivienda digna y adecuada para todos los navarros.

El objetivo general de la estrategia de innovación de la industria de la construcción

El objetivo general de la estrategia de innovación de la industria de la construcción es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo general de la estrategia de innovación de la industria de la construcción es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción.

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PROYECTOS

DIGIECOQUARRY: de la teoría a la práctica

En un contexto como el que estamos de cambio, adaptación y mejora continua, la digitalización, el análisis de datos y la automatización de procesos son herramientas clave para la optimización de nuestros recursos y la mejora de nuestros procesos. En este contexto, la digitalización de los procesos de negocio es una herramienta clave para la optimización de nuestros recursos y la mejora de nuestros procesos.

En este entorno empresarial, el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY formado por la Unión Europea, el Gobierno de Navarra, el Gobierno de Aragón y el Gobierno de Castilla-La Mancha, tiene como objetivo mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY formado por la Unión Europea, el Gobierno de Navarra, el Gobierno de Aragón y el Gobierno de Castilla-La Mancha, tiene como objetivo mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción.

El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción.

El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción.

Proyectos

Tecnología y datos para las canteras del futuro

En la minería 4.0, el papel que desempeña la tecnología y los datos es fundamental para la optimización de los procesos de explotación de las canteras. La tecnología y los datos son herramientas clave para la optimización de los procesos de explotación de las canteras.

El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción. El objetivo de este proyecto es mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción.

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Proyectos

Bienvenidos a la Olimpiada Geológica Madrileña

El proyecto europeo DIGIECOQUARRY, que tiene como objetivo mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción, ha participado recientemente en la Olimpiada Geológica Madrileña. El proyecto europeo DIGIECOQUARRY, que tiene como objetivo mejorar la competitividad y la sostenibilidad de la industria de la construcción, ha participado recientemente en la Olimpiada Geológica Madrileña.

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Proyectos

Proyecto ROTATE, innovación y sostenibilidad

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Proyectos

Proyecto ROTATE, innovación y sostenibilidad

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https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_68_v2

ANEFA actualidad no 69. Apr – May – Jun 2022

El equipo de ANEFA responde a cinco preguntas clave sobre el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY

¿Qué es DEQ?
DIGIECOQUARRY es un proyecto financiado por la Unión Europea bajo el programa Horizonte 2020 (10101003750) lanzado en junio de 2021. Su objetivo es diseñar, desarrollar y validar en cinco explotaciones de áridos un Sistema Inteligente para la Gestión de Canteras o Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS). El IQS está compuesto por sensores, procesos y herramientas, cuya finalidad es capturar, almacenar y procesar los datos generados a lo largo de todas las etapas de producción de áridos. Esto permitirá, una vez implementado el sistema, un control integrado, digitalizado, automático y en tiempo real de las actividades llevadas a cabo en una explotación.

Europa sea autosuficiente, en varios sectores poblacionales sigue habiendo un rechazo frontal a las actividades extractivas. Fenómenos como el *NOT IN MY BACKYARD*. No en mi patio trasero) torpedean la apertura o la continuidad de las explotaciones, lo que las obliga a justificar en detalle su cómo y su por qué.

¿Para qué vale DEQ?
Este proyecto nace como solución a los de los problemas fundamentales de la Unión Europea: el auge del consumo de materias primas y su dependencia de suministro exterior. A pesar de que cada vez se hace más patente la necesidad de que

Es aquí donde entra en juego DIGIECOQUARRY. No se trata simplemente de digitalizar una cantera, sino de, a través de su automatización, hacerla más eficiente, segura, energéticamente eficaz y socialmente responsable.

¿Por qué es tan importante? ¿Desafíos?
Actualmente la industria minera se enfrenta a multitud de desafíos. La gestión de las explotaciones mineras cada día tiene que ser más eficiente económicamente, respetuosa con el medio ambiente y socialmente responsables. Esto provoca la necesidad de integrar diferentes roles y equipos. Provocando que la toma de decisiones se vuelva cada vez más y más compleja.

Para facilitar y analizar las alternativas es necesario contar con un histórico de datos que permita diseñar y simular escenarios. Impli-

cando a todas las fuentes de información que existen en la organización y la maquinaria que trabajan en ella. En el caso de las máquinas el reto es mayor, ya que no tiene sentido hablar de eficiencia si se plantea a como única solución la compra de equipamiento, cuando el que existe actualmente continúa en perfecto estado de funcionamiento. Es por ello por lo que uno de los principios de DIGIECOQUARRY es poder digitalizar maquinaria que actualmente se encuentra en uso en la explotación. A todo esto, hay que añadir que, por la naturaleza de las explotaciones en zonas aisladas, suelen implicar desafíos de conexión.

Toda esta información (datos almacenados, procesados e interpretados) permite una gestión medioambiental y sostenible de las explotaciones. Actuando como hilo conductor en la toma de decisiones y la optimización de los procesos. Hoy en día ya no es suficiente con optimizar una parte del proceso de forma aislada, ya que se perdería la enorme ventaja

PROYECTOS

supone poder optimizar todo proceso en conjunto (o lo que más habitual, que se optimice a parte en detrimento de otra), a lo cual la organización necesita contar con una base de datos diversa fuentes, almacenarlos de una forma eficiente y poder extraerlos para generar los cuadros de mando que demanda cada uno de los departamentos.

sarrollando innovadoras técnicas de reconocimiento del frente que, junto con la tecnología MWD (Measurement While Drilling u obtención de las características de la roca mientras se perfora) y un nuevo explosivo, consiguen la optimización de la voladura. Esto incluye la disminución de la cantidad de explosivo a utilizar; la mejor rotura de la roca, lo que implica un menor rechazo; y la agilitación de la entrada de los materiales en el primario, consumiendo menos energía al evitar los atascos y la recirculación del material.

Por otro lado, al dotar a la planta de tratamiento de sensores, se monitoriza el proceso completo. Con esto se consigue la adaptación del ritmo de producción de las machacadoras y cribas al flujo de material, reduciendo el consumo de electricidad. Este proceso de

¿Cuál será el futuro?

DEQ se está perfilando como una excelente puerta de entrada para la digitalización de las canteras de áridos. Permitirá contar con una única herramienta diseñada desde su inicio teniendo en cuenta las necesidades de las explotaciones. El equipo de ANEFA ha considerado a la hora de definir los requisitos: el tamaño medio de las explotaciones, los recursos con los que cuenta y sobre todo sus necesidades. Una vez terminado el proyecto el sector dispondrá de una aplicación integral que permita gestionar todas las áreas de la organización. Esto ha sido posible gracias a unificar la visión tecnológica de los equipos multidisciplinares (desde los equipos de IA a fabricantes de equipamiento minero) que forman parte del consorcio.

res en el desarrollo de aplicaciones adaptándolos al sector minero. Está integrado por herramientas pensadas y adaptadas para la gestión e interconexión de todas las partes que forman la cantera (extracción, planta de tratamiento, transporte del material, KPI medioambientales y sociales, etc.). Se ha realizado un esfuerzo en desarrollar una base de datos única para la organización que permitirá la gestión de varias canteras. Con DEQ podéis generar los informes y las conexiones necesarias para la gestión integral de todos los datos de la organización. Evitando que los datos sean prisioneros de una única solución y facilitando su uso por todos los miembros que lo necesiten. Permite la implementación y diseño de cuadros de mando a medida de cada organización. Representa una solución que se adapta a las necesidades presentes y futuras.

El objetivo del proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY es diseñar, desarrollar y validar en cinco explotaciones de áridos un Sistema Inteligente para la Gestión de Canteras o Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS)

Stein und Kies

STEIN & KIES

von
PHILIPP HARTLIEB
Montanuniversität Leoben
- Lehrstuhl für Bergbau-
kunde, Bergtechnik und
Bergwirtschaft

H2020-Projekt DIGIECOQUARRY

ERFOLGREICH GESTARTET

Am 2. & 3.6.2021 fiel der offizielle Startschuss für DIGIECOQUARRY - INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATES SYSTEMS. Dieses neue europäische Projekt wird im Rahmen von Horizon 2020 (Nr. 101003750) gefördert, läuft vier Jahre (bis Mai 2025) und zielt darauf ab, ein innovatives Steinbruchsystem (IQS) zu entwerfen, zu entwickeln und zu validieren. Das Projekt umfasst Sensoren, Prozess-Werkzeuge und Methoden zur Datenerfassung, -verarbeitung und -weitergabe, um eine integrierte, digitalisierte, automatische Echtzeit-Prozesssteuerung für Steinbrüche zu ermöglichen.

Das DIGIECOQUARRY-Konsortium kombiniert neueste und fortschrittliche Technologie mit innovativen digitalen Lösungen, um die Kapazitäten zu erhöhen, die Gesundheits- und Sicherheitsbedingungen für die Arbeiter zu verbessern, die Selektivität und Effizienz des Abbaus zu erhöhen sowie Nachhaltigkeit, Ressourceneffizienz und soziale und Akzeptanz zu fördern.

Die Montanuniversität Leoben ist einer von 25 Partnern aus Spanien, Portugal, Frankreich, Deutschland, Italien, Österreich, Schweden, Finnland, Kolumbien und Südafrika. Zu den Projektpartnern zählen: Steinbrüche (Granulats Vicat, Hanson Hispania SA, Holcim Agregati Calcestruzzi SRL, Cronenberger Steinindustrie Franz Triches GmbH & Co and Agrepor Agregados - Extracção de Inertes, S.A), Technologie- und Bergbauunternehmen (Sandvik Mining and Construction OY, Metso Outotec Finland OY, Maxamcorp International S.L., ITK Engineering GMBH, Akka High Tech, Arco Electrónica SA, Ma-estro SRL, DOHMEN HERZOG & Partner GmbH, Abaut GmbH, Sigma Technologies S.L.U., Mintek, ROCTIM AB), Konsultanten (APP Consultoria de Gestión de Proyectos SL, Zabala Innovation Consulting SA), Hochschulen (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Montanuniversität Leoben, Chalmers Tekniska Högskola AB) und andere Einrichtungen (Asociación Colombiana de Productores de Agregados Pétreos, Consejería de Industria, Empleo y Promoción Económica del Principado de Asturias). Das Team des Lehrstuhls für Bergbaukunde wird sich dabei

mit der Digitalisierung des Bergbaus und der automatisierten Prozesserkennung beschäftigen, mit besonderem Fokus auf die Umweltauswirkungen einzelner Prozessschritte, sowie innovativen Werkzeugen auf Basis Bilderkennung.

Dazu sollen zwei wesentliche Aspekte erarbeitet werden:

- 1) Entwicklung automatischer Werkzeuge, basierend auf optischer Bildverarbeitung, die sowohl die einzelnen Sprengbohrlöcher charakterisieren, als auch die mit dem Sprengen assoziierten Umweltauswirkungen erfassen können;
- 2) möglichst vollständige, digitale Erfassung aller Prozessschritte im Bergbau (von Geologie, bis Hauwerk, Lade- und Fördertätigkeit, assoziierte Emissionen und vieles mehr), um die Daten dann sinnvoll zusammenzuführen und ein möglichst holistisches Bild des Systems zu erhalten.

Solcherart kann dann mit wenig Aufwand jeder Prozessschritt erfasst und digitalisiert sowie mit den andern Prozessschritten verglichen werden (z.B. das reine Laden/Graben mit dem Bagger in Bezug zum gesamten Ladezyklus gesetzt werden). Daraus sollen dann in weiterer Folge relevante Key Performance Indikatoren für die beteiligten Betriebe (aber natürlich auch für die Steinbruchwirtschaft im Allgemeinen) abgeleitet werden. Diese KPIs dienen sowohl der wirtschaftlichen Steuerung und Optimierung, sollen aber zeitgleich auch der Reduktion von Umweltauswirkungen, insbesondere Energie/CO₂ zuträglich sein.

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14Annex V. Articles in partners' communication channels

ANEFA Online 179. December 2021

Novedades en el proyecto DigiEcoQuarry

Reunión general del IAB

El pasado martes 16 de noviembre tuvo lugar la primera reunión del "International Advisory Board" (<https://digiecoquarry.eu/#iab>), debido a las restricciones se realizó telemáticamente. La reunión de trabajo contó con la presencia de destacados miembros internacionales (pertenecientes y no pertenecientes a la Unión Europea) dentro de la industria de los áridos. El objetivo de contar con este grupo heterogéneo dentro del proyecto DigiEcoQuarry (<https://digiecoquarry.eu/>) es proporcionar una visión externa teniendo en cuenta a todos los actores que forman parte de sector de los áridos.

En la reunión, los líderes de los grupos de trabajo expusieron los trabajos realizados vinculados con las temáticas de acción social, las actividades de clúster y los trabajos de comunicación. Se aprovechó para debatir sobre las estrategias y líneas de actuación generales para el próximo año. Para lo cual resultó muy útil los consejos y *feedback* recibido durante la reunión. Las reuniones del IAB forman parte del proyecto DigiEcoQuarry, con una periodicidad anual nos permiten conocer valoraciones externas del desarrollo que se está realizando y las líneas de trabajo que se están siguiendo.

<https://www.aridos.org/novedades-en-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/>

ANEFA Online 180 January 2022

Reunión del Comité Técnico del proyecto DigiEcoQuarry

El pasado martes 21 de diciembre se reunió telemáticamente el Comité Técnico del proyecto DigiEcoQuarry. Esta reunión tuvo lugar tras el acto presencial de todo el consorcio que desarrollo en el salón de actos de la ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid. La función principal de este comité (PTC, *Project Technical Committee*) es supervisar el correcto desarrollo del proyecto. Participaron 19 personas pertenecientes a los socios: Holcim Aggregati Calcestruzzi, Granulats Vicat, Akka High Tech, Dohmen Herzog & Partner, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Zabala Innovation Consulting y ANEFA

El comité técnico esta compuesto por todos los responsables de los paquetes de trabajo (WP) del proyecto DEQ y presidido por ANEFA por su papel como

coordinador general y la Universidad de Leoben de Austria como colíder. El PTC se reúne para recabar información sobre el progreso del proyecto y en el caso de existir desviaciones, asesorará a al PMB (*Project Management Board*) sobre la forma de reordenar las tareas y los presupuestos. Entre sus funciones también esta la de apoyar al PC (*Project Coordinator*) en la preparación de las reuniones con la CE y de los datos y productos relacionados, preparar los contenidos y el calendario de los comunicados de prensa y las publicaciones conjuntas, así como revisar toda la documentación del proyecto.

Durante esta reunión, los líderes de los paquetes de trabajo (del 1 al 5) debatieron sobre los riesgos que se han identificado hasta el momento. Como resultado de la reunión se definieron los próximos pasos para para abordar los riegos detectados con el fin de que no alteren el desarrollo del proyecto.

<https://www.aridos.org/reunion-del-comite-tecnico-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry/>

ANEFA Online 181. February 2022

DIGIECOQUARRY. Empieza a tomar forma la plataforma para la gestión inteligente de la cantera

Ha comenzado el paquete de trabajo 4 del proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY, el cual diseñará el IQS, la plataforma de gestión inteligente de la cantera. Los socios que componen este paquete estudiarán y compararán los marcos de trabajo y las herramientas comerciales más prometedoras del mercado. Con ellas, se construirá la base de las soluciones para la integración de los datos de los sensores, la plataforma de IoT, el *datalake* y el *datawarehouse* para el procesamiento de los algoritmos de inteligencia artificial.

Entre los objetivos de este paquete de trabajo se encuentran:

- Definir la arquitectura e integrar las soluciones de cada socio en la plataforma global.
- Recopilar, filtrar y etiquetar los datos de todos los sensores, tanto los instalados en la cantera como los externos, para el despliegue, implementación y entrenamiento de los algoritmos de IA.
- Vincular la plataforma con el modelo BIM desarrollado.
- Realizar simulaciones 4D de los procesos y actividades de la cantera.
- Realizar el análisis lógico de los trabajos y procedimientos de la explotación, el análisis forense y las métricas personalizadas.
- Diseñar e implementar todo el IQS.
- Proporcionar fácil acceso a todos los datos adquiridos en cuadros de mando especializados con datos en tiempo real e históricos.

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-empieza-a-tomar-forma-la-plataforma-para-la-gestion-inteligente-de-la-cantera/>

ANEFA Online 182. March 2022

Primer hito del proyecto DigiEcoQuarry superado

DEQ Logo

implicado un esfuerzo extra por parte de todos los participantes. La finalización de estos entregables no habría sido posible sin la estrecha colaboración de todos los socios que forman parte del proyecto.

Los informes (*deliberables*) que forman el paquete de trabajo 1 (WP1) son:

- D 1.1 "Requisitos para mejorar la extracción, la caracterización del macizo rocoso e informe de control" catalogado como de difusión pública y correspondiente a la tarea 1.1 "Requisitos para mejorar la extracción, la caracterización y el control del macizo rocoso y el tratamiento innovador (trituración/cribado/lavado)"
- D 1.2 "Requisitos para procesos de tratamiento innovadores" catalogado como de difusión pública y que también pertenece a la tarea 1.1
- D 1.3 "Requisitos para la digitalización completa de la cantera (sensores inteligentes, la automatización y el control de procesos, soluciones TIC, BIM e IA)" catalogado como de difusión pública y que esta englobado dentro de la tarea 1.2 "Requisitos para la digitalización completa de las canteras (para los sensores inteligentes, la automatización y el control de procesos, y para las soluciones TIC, BIM e IA"
- D 1.4 "Requisitos para Informe sobre la mejora de la seguridad y salud, minimización del impacto ambiental, la eficiencia energética y de los recursos" catalogado como Confidencial (sólo para los miembros del consorcio, incluidos los servicios de la Comisión). Este informe corresponde a la tarea 1.3 "Requisitos para la mejora de la seguridad y salud, la minimización del impacto medioambiental y la eficiencia energética y de los recursos (minerales, agua y otros)."

El informe correspondiente con el paquete de trabajo 7 es el D7.1 "Narración del contexto, matriz de riesgo social y cartografía de las partes interesadas", correspondiente a la tarea 7.1 "Análisis del riesgo social en los 5 sitios piloto" en el que se ha realizado un estudio minucioso de la situación de cada sitio piloto.

<https://www.aridos.org/primer-hito-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry-superado/>

ANEFA Online 183. April 2022

AVANCES EN LOS PROYECTOS EUROPEOS DE ANEFA

Dos de los proyectos europeos en los que ANEFA participa activamente como coordinador, DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) y AgeingAtWork siguen adelante con su periodo de investigación y análisis. De hecho, el segundo de ellos, AgeingAtWork, ya está en su recta final tras la celebración de la reunión con los revisores de la Comisión Europea a principios de marzo.

El objetivo del proyecto es la implantación de soluciones TIC inteligentes, personalizadas y adaptables para un envejecimiento activo, saludable y productivo con funcionalidad mejorada. A través de ANEFA se coordina uno de los dos pilotos implicados en el proyecto, y actualmente se están analizando los

resultados obtenidos de la primera fase de implantación de las herramientas TIC generadas por los miembros del consorcio.

Paralelamente, se ha iniciado con la segunda fase final de este, con el fin de que otros usuarios puedan experimentar con estas herramientas, y de esta manera obtener un número mayor de resultados.

Se tiene previsto convocar la última reunión del consorcio que forma este proyecto el día antes de la inauguración del VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos para aprovechar este evento como circunstancia ideal para informar de los resultados obtenidos y de las conclusiones obtenidas en el proyecto.

DIGIECOQUARRY PRESENTE EN LAS OLIMPIADAS GEOLÓGICAS

Por otro lado, DEQ, que continua en su fase de desarrollo, ha participado en la sección madrileña de las olimpiadas españolas de geología en las que estudiantes y profesores participaron en diversas competiciones de conocimientos en la Escuela de Minas y Energía de Madrid. En la misma se trató gran cantidad de información relativa a los áridos y las canteras además de ponerse en relevancia información relativa a la digitalización a través de ejemplos prácticos en los que se desarrollaron modelos 3D de minerales y rocas.

<https://www.aridos.org/olimpiadas-y-sprints-finales/>

ANEFA Online 184. May 2022

DIGIECOQUARRY continúa su trabajo de campo

El equipo de coordinación del proyecto europeo DIGIECOQUARRY, liderado por Anefa, visitó de nuevo dos de sus explotaciones piloto: la de Fenouillet en Toulouse, Francia, propiedad de Granulats Vicat y Alenquer, propiedad de Cimpor-Agrepor, en Lisboa, Portugal.

DIGIECOQUARRY es un proyecto financiado por la Unión Europea dentro del programa Horizon 2020 que se dedica a diseñar, desarrollar y validar un Sistema Inteligente de Explotación de Canteras (IQS por sus siglas en inglés: Intelligent Quarrying System). En este proceso es fundamental la participación de cinco explotaciones que sirven como piloto a la hora de elaborar las distintas fases del estudio. Estos IQS están formados por sensores, procesos y herramientas que capturan y procesan los datos recogidos durante la labor de producción de áridos. Esto, en un futuro, cuando el sistema esté implementado del todo, servirá para poder contar con un control integrado, digitalizado, automático y en tiempo real de las actividades propias de una cantera.

Durante este tiempo, las acciones que se tomarán en cada uno de los pilotos anteriormente mencionados se están afinando para poder aprovechar todo el potencial de cada explotación. Justo esta es la razón tras las visitas a Francia y Portugal. Los representantes de Anefa han mantenido reuniones y entrevistas personales con los responsables de cada organización para redefinir y aclarar los roles que debe asumir cada uno de los actores en tan ambicioso proyecto. Gracias a esta labor, que ha sido muy fructífera, el proyecto de DIGIECOQUARRY continúa su senda imparable hacia la digitalización.

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-continua-su-trabajo-de-campo/>

SIGMA

Digiecoquarry

by Daniel Tapias | Mar 29, 2022 | Sin categoría | 0 comments

The SIGMA GROUP of companies is participating in the DIGIECOQUARRY project, a significant breakthrough in process digitalization and automation capabilities for the aggregates sector. This project is financed by the Horizon 2020 programme and has on board 25 important European players in the quarry and digitalization industries.

DIGIECOQUARRY's ambition is to tap the full potential of "Digital Quarries" through a significant breakthrough in process digitalization and automation capabilities for the aggregates sector.

The Project is targeting the processes improvement through: Health, Safety and Security monitoring and implanting measures to reduce accidents and improve working conditions; facilitating Efficiency, selectivity and profitability ensuring long-term operational sustainability and viability; reducing the Environmental impact, maximizing resource efficiency while reducing emissions and improving the management of water and other supplies; fostering social acceptance through better communication with policy makers, citizens and relevant actors.

The Future of Quarries

SIGMA Technologies is bringing Artificial Intelligence to the Quarry processes by analyzing data coming from various sources in an advanced Data Architecture framework called the IQS (Intelligent Quarry Systems).

The IQS will feature a Datalake to gather data in heterogeneous formats, an IoT Platform gathering data coming from sensors installed in the quarry mobile and fixed equipment, and a Datawarehouse used to store processed data coming from the Artificial Intelligence models and algorithms.

SIGMA will develop models, services and algorithms that will help quarry managers and related partners to make better decisions, obtain alarms, analyze historical information around the following main areas:

Risk analysis, Specialized information search using Natural Language Processing, Equipment Predictive Maintenance, Stock Forecast and management and Computer Vision applied to the quarry installations to analyze distances, volumes and possible security threats.

Pierre Plaza

R&D programmes at Sigma

pplaza@sigma-ai.com

<https://sigmacognition.ai/digiecoquarry/>

